

Phytochemical Investigation on Flowers of *Gliricidia sepium**

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GLIRICIDIA sepium (Syn. *G. maculata*) sometimes known as Madre de cacao (South America) or Kakawate (Philippines) is a fast growing, leguminous, medium sized, thornless tree which can substitute for *Leucaena leucocephala* as a source of fodder, fuelwood and green manure, in hedges and living fences, and as a shade tree in tea, coffee and cocoa plantations¹.

Coumarin, *o*-coumaric acid, melilotic acid and rhamnogalactoside of kaempferol have been reported in the leaves by earlier workers^{2,3}, while the flowers contained only quercetin-3-glucoside⁴. Thus it was thought worthwhile to carry out the detailed chemical analysis of the flowers.

Experimental

The air dry powdered flowers (500 g) were extracted with hot petroleum ether and alcohol, respectively.

Petroleum ether extract showed the presence of waxy material. The alcohol extract was chromatographed over silica gel and elution with solvents of increasing polarity gave four compounds A–D. Compounds A to D were characterised by uv, acetate nmr, permethylation studies and direct comparison with respective authentic samples (co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir).

Compound A (200 mg), yellow needles, m.p. 178°, was identified as kaempferol-3-glucoside⁵ (astragalin).

The structure of compound B (150 mg), pale yellow needles, m.p. 260°, was found to be kaempferol-3-galactoside⁶ (trifolin). Compound C (5 g), yellow needles, m.p. 196°, $[\alpha]_D - 121^\circ$ (in MeOH), was characterised as kaempferol-3-robinobioside-7-rhamnoside⁷ (robinin). Compound D (10 g), colourless prisms, m.p. 183° $[\alpha]_D + 67^\circ$ (in water), was identified as sucrose.

Conclusion: This is the first report of the occurrence of these compounds in the *Gliricidia sepium* flowers. The flowers can be utilised for the extraction of robinin which occurs in them in 1% yield.

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References

1. J. L. FALVEY, *Int. Free Crops J.*, 1982, 2, 1.
2. L. A. GRIFFITHS, *J. Exptl. Bot.*, 1962, 13, 169.
3. S. BANGASWAMI and V. S. IYER, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, 14, 364.
4. A. G. R. NAIR and S. S. SUBRAMANIAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1962, 31, 504.
5. T. NAKABAYASHI, *J. Agric. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1952, 26, 539.
6. S. HATTORI and M. HASEGAWA, *Acta Phytochim.*, 1949, 13, 99.
7. G. ZEMPLEN and R. BOGNAR, *Chem. Ber.*, 1941, 74, 1783.

A New Method for Determination of Sulphites in Polluted Waters

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SULPHITES are commonly found in waste water from pulp and paper mills, in boiler and boiler feed water, and also in cooling process and distribution water system at cold water temperature¹. Sulphite reduces the dissolved oxygen content and COD of water².

Most of the methods including the standard method reported for determination and detection of sulphites in water and waste water are based on iodometric titrations^{1,3,4}, which are subjected to interference from organic matter and other reduced compounds⁵ and are less sensitive. Very few colorimetric methods⁶ are reported for determination of sulphites. Decolourisation of trimethylphenyl dyes by the sulphite solution forms a basis of its analysis colorimetrically⁵.

In this communication a sensitive and selective method for determination of sulphite in water is reported. The method is based upon the liberation of sulphur dioxide from acidified sulphite solution and its absorption in aqueous solution of malonyldihydroxamic acid (MDHA) and is then determined spectrophotometrically using *p*-aminoazobenzene and formaldehyde following the method of Kniseley and Throop⁷. This reagent system has already been reported for the determination of sulphur dioxide in air⁸. The reported method is highly sensitive and selective for sulphites in water, waste and river water. Most of the common pollutants present in water such as nitrate, nitrite, sulphate, fluoride, phosphate, ammonia and metallic cations do not interfere.

Experimental

Apparatus: An ECIL GS 865 spectrophotometer and Carl Zeiss Spekol with 1 cm matched glass cells were used for spectrophotometric measurements.